

An Improvised Viscometric Technique of Studying the Effect of Temperature on Liquid Flow Behaviour

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Manuscript received 30 December 1994, revised 22 August 1995, accepted 27 October 1995

To understand the macroscopic molecular motion in liquids, the viscosity coefficients and their dependence on the related parameters are investigated. The microscopic molecular dynamic relaxation depends on the coefficient of viscosity and is largely influenced by temperature variations¹. Density, temperature, normal boiling point, molecular shape, size and their interactions are the determinant factors of liquid viscosity. Inaccurate observations of viscous flow behaviour of liquids quite often lead to misinterpretations. Hence, a systematic and refined methods of studying the temperature influenced viscous flow need to be adopted. Mostly, classical Ostwald type viscometers are used for this purpose. As the method involves comparison of viscosities, it is naturally believed that the common errors get eliminated. However, a lot of inconvenience and ambiguity prevail apparently in the measurements at increased temperatures. The frictional behaviour of liquids is highly dependent upon the thermal status of molecules and one can claim at high accuracy only when the variation in the involved parameters (density, pressure, flowtime and temperature) are measured exactly without any significant errors.

The present work is aimed to overcome the difficulties by designing a new type of viscometer. The validity and reliability of the design have been tested by verifying the known viscosity of some pure organic simple liquids and liquid mixtures.

Results and Discussion

To assess the validity of the newly designed viscometer, it has been subjected to the model test by evaluating the Reynold's number² (R_c),

$$R_c = \frac{\rho v L}{\eta} \quad (1)$$

where ρ is the density of liquid (kg m^{-3}), v the velocity of flow (m s^{-1}) L the representative length of flow (m) and η the viscosity coefficient of liquid (cp).

The observed efflux times (t , s) and literature values of viscosity coefficients at different temperatures of distilled water are used to evaluate the Reynold's number ($R = 1753$). It is found to be lesser than 2000, fulfilling the main requisite for a laminar flow in the viscometer.

The constant of the viscometer is computed at various temperatures from the relation,

$$V_K = \frac{\eta_w}{t_w \rho_w} \quad (2)$$

where η_w is the literature value of viscosity coefficient for water (cp), t_w the observed efflux time (s) and ρ_w the measured density (g ml^{-1}) of water at a particular temperature.

Fig 1

The viscosity coefficients of the chosen liquids are calculated using the relation³,

$$\eta_l = V_k t_l \rho_l \quad (3)$$

where t_l and ρ_l are the time of flow and density of liquid at a constant temperature.

Using the efflux time for water (t_w) as the standard, and the same for other liquids (t_l) under study, the viscosity coefficients (η_l) are found to decrease with the increase of temperature. This indicates that the transfer of momentum between the layers of molecules is fast owing to the decrease in density at the viscous drag region.

In the present viscometric study, the determined coefficients show the usual variation. These results are in very close agreement with the earlier observations⁴.

With the available literature values of η_1 the present experimental results at different temperatures are compared for the chosen liquids. It is observed that there is a slight deviation in the case of 1,4-dioxan and mixs. II and III (Tables 1 and 2).

TABLE 1—VISCOSITY COEFFICIENTS (η_1 exp, η_1 lit), VISCOSITY ERROR ($\Delta\eta\%$), KINEMATIC VISCOSITY (ν_1), FOR THE LIQUIDS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

T K	η_1 (exp) cp	η_1 (lit) cp	ν_1 %	ν_1 $\times 10^5$
Benzene				
303	0.564	0.564	0.00	0.653
313	0.504	0.503	-0.20	0.588
323	0.443	0.442	-0.23	0.526
333	0.392	0.392	0.00	0.470
343	0.358	0.358	0.00	0.435
Carbon tetrachloride				
303	0.845	0.845	0.00	0.538
313	0.741	0.739	-0.27	0.476
323	0.656	0.651	-0.76	0.427
333	0.590	0.585	-0.85	0.388
343	0.530	0.524	-1.13	0.352
Cyclohexane				
303	0.813	0.831	2.21	1.060
313	0.683	0.715	4.69	0.900
323	0.586	0.619	5.63	0.781
333	0.496	0.538	8.47	0.669
343	0.421	0.470	11.64	0.575
1,4-Dioxan				
303	1.035	1.017	-1.74	1.015
313	0.957	0.868	-9.30	0.946
323	0.886	0.745	-15.91	0.886
333	0.808	0.644	-20.30	0.817
343	0.734	0.559	-23.84	0.746

The Lewis-Squires's empirical relation⁴,

$$\eta_1^x = \eta_k^x + \frac{T_1 - T_k}{233} \quad (4)$$

where $x = 0.2661$, η_1 is the liquid viscosity to be known at temperature (T_1), η_k the known viscosity of the same liquid at a temperature (T_k), is used to deduce the viscosity coefficients at required temperatures wherever the literature values are not available. Though it is an approximate estimation with allowed errors 5 to 15% (or more), still it is quite agreeable with the present observed values of viscosity for mixs. I, II and III. Using Grunburg-Nissan's equation⁵ for interacting liquid mixtures, η_{1mix} values are calculated,

$$\ln \eta_{1mix} = X_1 \ln \eta_1 + X_2 \ln \eta_2 + 2X_1X_2 \ln \eta_{12} \quad (5)$$

where X_1 and X_2 are mole fractions of components 1 and 2 (aniline and nitrobenzene), η_1 and η_2 the viscosities of components 1 and 2 and $\eta_{12} = 0.5\eta_1 + 0.5\eta_2$. These values

(η_{1mix}) are reasonably comparable with the experimental values (Table 2). The excess coefficient of viscosity (η_{ex}) is less positive and more negative with temperature variation showing some kind of molecular association; the fluctuation shows the disturbed momentum transfer due to the thermally agitated translational motion of spherical molecules hindered by a very weak charge transfer complexation confirming the study by Prakash and Rai⁶ for aniline nitrobenzene mixtures.

TABLE 2—VISCOSITY (η_1 exp and η_1 lit), VISCOSITY ERROR ($\Delta\eta\%$), KINEMATIC VISCOSITY (ν_1) FOR ANILINE, NITROBENZENE AND THEIR MIXTURES I,II AND III AND EXCESS VISCOSITY (η_{ex}) FOR THE MIXTURES AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

T K	η_1 (exp)	η_1 (lit)	$\Delta\eta$ %	ν_1 10^5	η_{ex} cp
Aniline					
303	3.047	3.160	3.70	3.017	—
313	2.420	2.370	-2.07	2.418	—
323	1.904	1.850	-2.84	1.918	—
333	1.588	1.510	-4.91	1.612	—
343	1.357	1.270	-6.41	1.389	—
Nitrobenzene					
303	1.614	1.679	2.32	1.377	—
313	1.327	1.401	5.58	1.120	—
323	1.148	1.179	2.70	0.978	—
333	0.964	1.000	3.70	0.827	—
343	0.845	0.854	1.07	0.739	—
mix.I-Aniline-Nitrobenzene (1 : 3) ^x					
303	1.641	1.679	2.32	1.433	0.038
313	1.382	1.291	-6.58	1.218	-0.091
323	1.162	1.040	-10.50	1.033	-0.122
333	0.991	0.838	-15.44	0.886	-0.153
343	0.869	0.701	-19.33	0.784	-0.165
mix.II-Aniline-Nitrobenzene (1 : 1)					
303	1.820	1.876	3.08	1.654	0.056
313	1.466	1.414	-3.55	1.344	-0.052
323	1.322	1.096	-17.10	1.222	-0.226
333	0.188	0.867	-13.56	0.932	-0.136
343	0.857	0.713	-16.80	0.804	-0.144
mix.III-Aniline-Nitrobenzene (3 : 1)					
303	2.095	2.190	4.53	1.982	0.095
313	1.780	1.643	-7.70	1.697	-0.137
323	1.447	1.340	-7.39	1.390	-0.107
333	1.091	1.074	-1.56	1.056	-0.170
343	0.989	0.889	-10.11	0.966	-0.100

Hence, using this improvised viscometer standardised by evaluating (eqn. 2) the constant (5483.7, 5291.1, 4940.9, 4750.4, 4582.7 $V_k \text{ g s}^{-1}$) at different temperatures (303, 313, 323, 333, 343, 353 K), the flow behaviour of simple liquids may be successfully analysed (eqn. 3). This removes most of the difficulties encountered with the other viscometers and enables one to use it with the following merits : (i) the viscometer is always in vertical position, (ii) no suction by mouth is needed and the working is quite handy, (iii) attainment of constant temperature is seen when there is no more dropping of liquid through the capillary end, (iv) the flow of liquid from the top smaller bulb facilitates the stream-line motion to commence before the

flow time observation and (v) the saturated vapour on the surface of the liquid in the bottle prevents all discrepancies due to evaporation of liquid.

Experimental

The newly designed viscometer model (Fig.1) is based on the working principle of Ostwald and Lakhanapal⁷. The viscometer rested vertically on a flat bottomed bulb with a central uniform capillary (0.1 cm dia, 11.8 cm long) and two side limbs (0.5 cm dia) fused to it. The capillary end was at the 2/3 height of the bottom bulb, the other end being fused to a spherical bulb (11.2 ml between h1 and h2). This spherical bulb was fused together at the neck to the side-limbs through a smaller bulb and an air-tight stopper. With the experimental liquid in the bulb, top end closed and stopper opened; the viscometer inverted for filling the central spherical bulb and capillary. The viscometer was turned upright, opening the top and closing the stopper, the liquid being contained in the central bulb and capillary. The viscometer was rested vertically in a constant-temperature water-bath (INSREF-make, $\pm 0.01^\circ$). The liquid in the spherical bulb and capillary drops due to thermal expansion and stops dropping when attained thermal equilibrium with the bath. At this stage, opening the stopper fully, the flow time (h1 to h2) was observed using a digital stop watch (1/100 s). The volume of liquid to be taken in the viscometer was measured to be 23.3 ml, so that after filling the spherical bulb, liquid surface in the bottom bulb came in contact with the capillary-end to have con-

tinuity of flow. This is to avoid a little pressure fluctuation, if any, due to dropping of liquid.

The flow times for distilled water, benzene, carbon tetrachloride, cyclohexane, 1,4-dioxan, aniline, nitrobenzene and mixtures of aniline-nitrobenzene (1 : 3-Mix-I, 1 : 1-Mix-II, 3 : 1-Mix-III) at different temperatures but below the normal boiling points were observed. The densities at the respective temperatures were measured simultaneously using a pycnometer and semimicro single pan balance.

Acknowledgement

The authors express their thanks to M/s. Ponsil Scientific Glass blowing company, Pondicherry, for fabricating the viscometer. One of the authors (K.D.) is thankful to the Government of Pondicherry for permitting to pursue his research programme

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